

Gaussian Process Supported Stochastic MPC for Distribution Grids

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(Intersection of Machine Learning with Control)

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ABSTRACT The efficacy of control systems for distribution grids can be influenced by different sources of uncertainty. Stochastic Model Predictive Control (SMPC) can be employed to compensate for such uncertainties by integrating their probability distribution into the control problem. An efficient SMPC algorithm for online control applications is the stochastic tube SMPC, which is able to treat the evaluation of the chance constraints analytically. However, this approach is efficient only when the calculation of the constraint back-off is applied to a linear model. To address this issue, this work employs Gaussian Processes to approximate the nonlinear part of the power flow equations based on offline training, which is integrated into the SMPC formulation. The resulting SMPC is first validated and then tested on a benchmark system, comparing the results with Deterministic MPC and SMPC that excludes Gaussian Processes. The proposed SMPC proves to be more efficient in terms of cost minimization, reference tracking and voltage violation reduction.

INDEX TERMS Machine learning, optimization under uncertainties, predictive control for nonlinear systems, electric power networks, stochastic systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global energy sector is rapidly transitioning toward the integration of renewable resources, a shift that also brings considerable challenges for managing the electrical grid. This is particularly relevant at the distribution level, where intermittent Distributed Generation (DG) and loads are connected both at the Low Voltage (LV) and Medium Voltage (MV) level [1]. Consequently, electrical grid quantities that have historically been regarded as highly predictable have exhibited an increase in their variability. This shift has the effect of causing violations of voltage operational limits and overloading, which are limiting factors in distribution grid operations [2].

Therefore, advanced control strategies have been proposed to address such occurrences by controlling the power injections of DGs and Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs). These strategies require monitoring devices to obtain

knowledge about the grid status, which can then be employed to implement corrective actions for the controllable assets [3].

Together with the measurement data, the forecast data of loads and DGs can be utilized in the Model Predictive Control (MPC) to counter potential undesired grid behavior in advance [4]. However, forecast and measurement data are typically subject to uncertainties due to weather conditions, users' behavior and instrument errors [5], [6], thus impacting the performance of the controllers [7].

Together with applying control strategies under uncertainties, the second key challenge in distribution grid control is the modeling of the inherently high-dimensional system, characterized by its nonlinear behavior [8].

The primary issue with the model concerns the power flow equations, which must be solved either as a single-step optimization, namely the Optimal Power Flow (OPF), or within a receding horizon framework through MPC. For this reason,

extensive research has been focused on identifying effective solutions for these large-scale non-convex optimization problems [8], [9]. Meanwhile, the growing penetration of DGs has increased the need for fast and reliable computational methods, as these problems need to be solved every few minutes [10].

Conventional approaches for solving power flow equations typically fall into two categories: linear approximations for computational efficiency and convex relaxations for greater accuracy at the expense of computational resources. However, as noted by [11], there is a growing demand for approaches that are fully or partially supported by machine learning techniques to address efficient and accurate power flow solutions for control problems operating on finer timescales. The review in [12] also stresses the benefit of using learning-based approaches for power flow solutions in the context of distribution grid control. Deep learning is presented in [13] as a promising method to improve speed and accuracy of power flow solutions, for example, carried out by [14] and [15]. Similarly, the review in [16] puts forward power flow solutions as one promising application of Gaussian Processes in power systems as in [17] and [18].

A. RELATED WORK

1) STOCHASTIC MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL

MPC strategies have emerged as a solution to control dynamic systems by embedding future state predictions into the optimization process. However, Deterministic Model Predictive Control (DMPC) overlooks uncertainties associated with the model, the inputs, and external disturbances. To address this limitation, researchers have integrated stochastic variables into MPC algorithms [19]. Both Robust Model Predictive Control (RMPC) and Stochastic Model Predictive Control (SMPC) enhance the traditional approach by considering uncertainties. RMPC relies on worst-case assumptions while SMPC uses probability distributions to manage constraints, which has been proved to be generally more efficient [20].

Literature on control theory proposes different SMPC approaches, which in general can be differentiated into scenario–or sample-based– approaches and analytical approaches. In the context of SMPC for voltage control, the most prevalent approach is to use scenarios constructed through historical data, where each scenario appends its corresponding constraints to the optimization problem [21], [22], [23], [24]. Consequently, the scenario-based approach leads to high computation times, thereby posing a challenge for online control of large distribution grids. Furthermore, the satisfaction of the probabilistic constraints depends on the chosen scenarios and cannot always be guaranteed, which leads to operational risks in applications like voltage control [25].

To the best of the author’s knowledge, [26] is the only work where an analytical SMPC approach is applied to voltage control. However, this approach, which uses an affine-disturbance parameterization of the control policy, requires linearized power flow equations.

2) MODEL-FREE DATA-DRIVEN CONTROL

Beyond the probabilistic frameworks of SMPC, fully data-driven control approaches have emerged to address systems with complex or unknown dynamics. These approaches operate without system models and instead use historical data to capture the overall system behavior while also implicitly addressing uncertainties.

The work in [27] presents an algorithm that is proven to be equivalent to classic MPC in the case of deterministic linear time-invariant systems. Similar work in [28] additionally proves the recursive feasibility and stability of their algorithm. A tube-based MPC framework is proposed in [29], while [30] and [31] ensure computational feasibility through convex optimization. Meanwhile, Reinforcement Learning (RL) has emerged as another promising data-driven control approach [32], [33]. Nevertheless, all of the mentioned approaches are only tested on small-scale systems, and their computational demands may become prohibitive for high-dimensional systems like distribution grids. Finally, data-driven distributed MPC approaches for networked systems [34], still face significant scaling challenges for realistic distribution networks.

Recently, [10] proposed a deep RL solution for OPF equations, while [35] employed support vector machines and ridge regression to create a linearized data-driven model. However, these approaches primarily address one-step optimization rather than dynamic control.

Work by [36], [37], [38] shows that partitioning large networks into regions addresses computational challenges in high-dimensional control problems. However, these approaches remain limited in scalability and applicability, as their effectiveness depends heavily on similarities between historical training scenarios and actual operational conditions.

3) HYBRID DATA DRIVEN CONTROL

Hybrid data-driven control combines model-based approaches with data-driven methods, leveraging the strengths of both, thereby addressing challenges such as model inaccuracies, limited training data, and the need for control under uncertainty [39]. The core idea is to model well-known parts of the system based on physical equations and describe unknown or nonlinear parts by means of machine learning.

This hybrid model identification approach without actual control is applied to power flow equations in [40], where the nonlinear components are approximated via parameterization, leaving the rest as algebraic equations. Following this concept, a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) approach for approximating the same term appears in [17].

GPR, in general, has gained popularity for system identification as noted in [41] due to its sample efficiency compared with Artificial Neural Networks [42]. When combining GPR with control applications where the input parameters of the Gaussian process coincide with the decision variables of the MPC, the optimization problem can become nonlinear or non-convex depending on the chosen kernel. Therefore, recent

works such as [43] and [44] only deal with low-dimensional problems.

Nevertheless, maintaining convexity remains crucial for efficiently solving high-dimensional optimization problems, while linearity also enables the application of analytical stochastic tube algorithms. To address these challenges, this work presents a Gaussian Process supported SMPC for distribution grids under uncertainty with the following contributions.

B. CONTRIBUTION

This work presents a novel GPR-based model of the nonlinear power flow equations and its integration within the stochastic tube SMPC.

To achieve this goal, the power flow equations employed in the online application of the SMPC are kept in linear form by shifting the calculation of nonlinear parts offline. Hence, the a-priori knowledge of the controlled system and trajectories is used to generate data and train GPRs offline for each day as soon as the forecasts are available so as to later predict the nonlinear part of the power flow equations in the online control.

The GPR model of the proposed approach is related to considerations in [17]. However, the presented approach differs in the following aspect: To maintain the convexity of the control problem, an approximation scheme is proposed that addresses the line losses by employing a GPR defined by a linear kernel.

This approach enables the necessary trade-offs between efficient inference of the machine learning model in the control application and the required accuracy in solving the power flow equations as well as the effective integration into the stochastic tube algorithm. The result is a novel algorithm with the following contributions:

- A hybrid solution of the high-dimensional power flow equations by predicting the nonlinear terms with a GPR. The discussion on the approximation scheme includes sampling strategy and data set properties.
- The integration of the GPR approximation scheme into the stochastic tube SMPC algorithm, which is able to explicitly deal with any a-priori known probability distributions.
- The improvement, by means of the GPR prediction, of the loss minimization and the tracking of an external transmission grid support trajectory.
- The validation and testing on an IEEE 34 feeder topology with dedicated realistic load and generation profiles.

C. OUTLINE

This paper is organized as follows: After introducing remarks concerning the notation, Section II explains the theoretical backgrounds of stochastic tube SMPC, distribution grid modeling, and Gaussian processes. Section III presents the proposed approach by starting with the Lossless SMPC and then reintroducing the losses with support of GPR. Section IV describes the examined case study. Section V firstly validates

the individual results of the employed SMPC and GPR methods and then demonstrates the overall effectiveness of the proposed algorithm with a stochastic simulation. Section VI provides the concluding remarks.

D. NOTATION

This paper adopts the following notation conventions. Bold symbols represent node respectively line variables for all instances summarized in vectors or matrices, while non-bold symbols denote quantities associated with a single node or line. Furthermore, let $\mathcal{G} = (N, L, (h, j))$ be a spanning tree as typical for distribution grids, $\mathcal{N} = \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$ denotes the set of nodes, with 0 being the root node, $\mathcal{L} = \{1, \dots, L\}$ denotes the set of edges, respectively lines, with $L = N$. Let moreover $\mathbf{M}_0 \in \{0, \pm 1\}^{L \times N+1}$ denote the incidence matrix of the graph \mathcal{G} , defined via its elements

$$[\mathbf{M}_0]_{l,n} = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } n = f(l) \\ 1, & \text{if } n = t(l) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

with $f(l)$ and $t(l)$ the mapping functions that define the from and to nodes $n \in \mathcal{N}$ of the edge $l \in \mathcal{L}$. The incidence matrix $\mathbf{M} \in \{0, \pm 1\}^{L \times N}$, square by construction, refers to the graph \mathcal{G} with root node excluded.

The identity matrix is denoted as \mathbf{I} with subscripts defining the dimension. The diagonal operator, represented as *diag*, transforms vectors into diagonal matrices. The symbol $\mathbf{1}$ represents a vector of ones with the dimension N . For specific nodal references, e_n represents a zero-vector with a one at the nodal position n .

The notation $\|\mathbf{x}\|_{\mathbf{W}}$ denotes the vector norm of x with respect to the weighting matrix \mathbf{W} . The superscript T , denotes the transpose operation. Finally, the symbol \oplus defines the direct sum operator, which constructs block matrices from the given component matrices or vectors.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The following sections present the theoretical foundations of this work, starting with stochastic tube SMPC, the description of the controlled system and its model followed by the fundamentals of Gaussian Processes.

A. STOCHASTIC TUBE SMPC

The SMPC employed in this work is the stochastic tube SMPC, which combines probabilistic uncertainty descriptions with tube-based constraint tightening [20]. For additive disturbances, the method pre-computes constraint back-offs offline by analyzing the statistical properties of the uncertainty. These new bounds define a stochastic tube around the nominal trajectory and can be constructed by using techniques like Monte Carlo sampling, surrogate inequalities (e.g., Chebyshev bounds), or analytically by explicitly evaluating the propagation of probability distribution functions [19]. The tube width reflects a user-specified confidence level, which the online optimization follows.

FIGURE 1. Example of a radial distribution grid and its graph relative model.

FIGURE 2. Graphical representation of the *DistFlow* equations.

B. DISTRIBUTION GRIDS

Distribution grids are typically characterized by a radial structure, which can be mathematically modeled as a spanning tree \mathcal{G} . Within this model, the edges represent the electrical lines while the nodes represent the buses, as described in Fig. 1. At the root of the graph, a substation connects the distribution grid at the root node to the higher hierarchy-level transmission grid by means of a power transformer. The other grid nodes contain different kinds of distributed resources, which inject or draw power from the grid. This could be DG like wind turbines and large Photo-Voltaic (PV) plants, storage systems (e.g. large BESS), or just loads.

C. POWER FLOW EQUATIONS

The power flow equations constitute the basis of distribution grid control and describe how the voltages at the different nodes react to active and reactive power injections at the grid nodes. The relationship between voltages and power injections for radial grids is nonlinear (namely *DistFlow* equations), however, a linear model has been initially introduced in [45] and extended for a parameterized losses-approximation in [40]. Hence, the following equations, represented in Fig. 2, summarize the dependencies between voltages, power injections, and grid topology in matrix-vector notation according to [40], where the bold vectors hold the respective variables of all nodes respectively lines.

$$\mathbf{V}^2 = v_0^2 \cdot \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{c}^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{R} = 2 \cdot \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \text{diag}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{T} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{X} = 2 \cdot \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \text{diag}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{T} \quad (3)$$

In the considered distribution grid the set of grid nodes, with root node excluded, is defined as $\mathcal{N}^* = \{1, \dots, N\}$. Therefore, $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ represent the sum at each node $n \in \mathcal{N}^*$ of the power injected by the DGs and BESSs (positive) and the power consumed by the load (negative). Thereby $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ contains the voltage magnitude at all grid nodes $n \in \mathcal{N}^*$ and v_0 the voltage magnitude at the root node, the so-called slack bus. Hence matrix $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$ and $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$, denoting the resistance and reactance of the distribution lines, are derived from the incidence matrix \mathbf{M} of \mathcal{G} , the real and imaginary parts of the vector of line impedances \mathbf{r} and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^L$ respectively and the further connection matrices $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$ and $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times N}$ of the network, defined according to [40]. Matrix $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$, also defined in [40], summarizes a term consisting of connection matrices as well as line impedances. The term $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^L$ represents the line currents. Squaring the current and multiplying by the line impedances results in the actual power losses. This last additive loss term introduces a non-linearity into the equations, thereby causing (1) to conform to the *DistFlow* model description, whose optimal solution is a widely studied optimization problem [9]. The equation of c^2 for a single line $l \in \mathcal{L}$ between nodes $(h, j) \in \mathcal{N}$, as described in Fig. 2, is given by

$$c_l^2 = \frac{v_h^2 + v_j^2 - 2 \cdot v_h \cdot v_j \cos(\theta_{hj})}{r_l^2 + x_l^2} \quad (4)$$

which depends on the voltages v_h and v_j , connected by the respective line, as well as the corresponding phase angle $\cos(\theta_{hj})$.

All of the above equations are only valid for the so-called per-unit system. The per-unit system is a method used in power system analysis to normalize system values relative to base quantities. Instead of using absolute values (volts, amperes, ohms), quantities are expressed as fractions of their respective base values.

This approach simplifies calculations by eliminating the need for conversion between voltage levels. It also provides an intuitive understanding of system conditions, as values close to 1.0 pu represent normal operating conditions [46].

D. GAUSSIAN PROCESSES

A Gaussian process is a collection of random variables, any finite number of which have a Gaussian distribution [47]. As such, a Gaussian process provides a probability distribution over functions. Correspondingly, the data set under consideration does not have to follow a Gaussian distribution [48]. Denote the training data set by

$$(\mathbf{X}, Y) = \{(\mathbf{x}, y)_m | (\mathbf{x}, y)_m \in \mathbb{R}^{M_1} \times \mathbb{R}; \\ m = 1, \dots, M_2; M_1, M_2 \in \mathbb{N}\} \quad (5)$$

In the given application, Y represents the M_1 -many data points of offline simulated (squared) currents, while the corresponding active and reactive power injections of dimension M_2

provide M_1 -many X . The finite test set

$$\mathbf{X}^* = \{\mathbf{x}_m^* | \mathbf{x}_m^* \in \mathbb{R}^{M_1}; \tilde{m} = 1, \dots, M_3; M_3 \in \mathbb{N}\} \quad (6)$$

corresponds, in the proposed approach, to the power injections during operation, for which the (squared) currents must be estimated in the control scheme. As such, M_3 corresponds to the iteration steps of the SMPC.

A Gaussian process is fully determined by a prior mean function and a prior covariance function [47]. In the given application, it suffices to choose the prior mean function to be zero. For two, possibly distinct $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}' \in \mathbf{X}$ or \mathbf{X}^* as defined in (5) and (6), a symmetric positive semi-definite function

$$\kappa : \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{x}' \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (7)$$

is called the prior covariance function. With (7), the kernel (covariance matrix function) is defined as

$$K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}')_{ij} = (\kappa(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)) : \forall \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}, \forall \mathbf{x}_j \in \mathbf{X}' \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that (7), and thus (8) might depend on hyperparameters, which are specified during training.

Gaussian processes might be equipped with a noise hyperparameter $\sigma_n^2 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ via

$$K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \mathbf{I}\sigma_n^2 \quad (9)$$

added to the training kernel $K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X})$. It should be noted that this hyperparameter σ_n^2 accounts for every aspect of the corresponding signals, i.e., the training set (\mathbf{X}, Y) that is not captured by the Gaussian process. In the given application, σ_n^2 accounts for deviations from the linear approximation applied to under- and over-voltages.

For convenient use in this work, two independent Gaussian process kernels $K_1(\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}'_1)$ and $K_2(\mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}'_2)$ can be represented independently by utilizing the direct sum [47] by

$$K_1(\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}'_1) \oplus K_2(\mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}'_2) = \begin{pmatrix} K_1(\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}'_1) & 0 \\ 0 & K_2(\mathbf{X}_2, \mathbf{X}'_2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Gaussian processes have an inherent and natural objective function that can be derived from their Bayesian probabilistic framework [47]. Called the Negative Log Marginal Likelihood (NLML), this objective function can be computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{NLML} &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot Y^T \cdot [K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \mathbf{I}\sigma_n^2]^{-1} \cdot Y \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \cdot \ln(\det [K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \mathbf{I}\sigma_n^2]) \\ &+ \frac{\dim(\mathbf{X})}{2} \cdot \ln(2\pi) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The first term of (11) accounts for fitting the Gaussian process to the data, while the second, competing term ensures model simplicity to avoid over-fitting. The third term is a constant resulting from the computation of (11). The Gaussian process is trained by minimizing (11) with respect to the hyperparameters specifying the kernel. In the given application, this is used to pre-train the proposed Gaussian process with simulated

FIGURE 3. Overview of the proposed approach.

data. Once the optimal kernel hyperparameters are determined by the training, the posterior mean μ_{post}

$$\mu_{\text{post}} = K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}) \cdot [K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \mathbf{I}\sigma_n^2]^{-1} \cdot Y \quad (12)$$

and the posterior covariance Σ_{post} are computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{\text{post}} &= K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}^*) - K(\mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{X}) \cdot \\ &[K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \mathbf{I}\sigma_n^2]^{-1} \cdot K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}^*) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

After laying the foundation, this section elaborates on the proposed approach of this work, summarized in Fig. 3. The stochastic modeling of the distribution grid and uncertainty, on top of the figure, constitutes the foundation for the proposed SMPC. Based on the uncertainty model, the Lossless SMPC, light blue box, is developed to treat chance constraints by constructing stochastic tubes offline. To integrate the loss term in the stochastic tube computation, the GPR, in the purple box, is trained with offline simulations. Finally, the result of the SMPC offline calculation is used in the online MPC. The overall control framework constitutes the proposed Lossy SMPC.

A. STOCHASTIC MODELLING

This section develops a model of the distribution grid that can be integrated into the SMPC algorithm by adapting the power flow equations into an iterative model, completing the state-space equations with the BESS description, and adding uncertainty to the model.

1) DISTRIBUTION GRID

The distribution grid considered in this work includes: (i) DGs, specifically wind turbines and PV plants; (ii) large BESSs, directly connected to the MV node; (iii) aggregated loads at the MV level.

The model is based on the power flow equations described in Section II-C, in which the power injections \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} define

the aggregation of the power injections of the different elements of the grid, as follows:

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}^{\text{DG}} + \mathbf{p}^{\text{BESS}} - \mathbf{p}^{\text{LD}} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}^{\text{DG}} - \mathbf{q}^{\text{LD}} \quad (15)$$

where LD denotes the load. BESS are assumed to only inject or draw active power following [4], [49].

In order to derive the iterative state-space representation of the squared voltage magnitude to be employed in the SMPC, (1) is considered for two following time-steps, since, as described in [50], \mathbf{V}_k^2 depends only on power injections at time k . Therefore, (1) is considered for power injections at two different time-steps, neglecting the dynamics that occur between the two steady-state conditions. Consequently, \mathbf{V}_{k+1}^2 can be expressed as a function of the two time-steps k and $k+1$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{V}_{k+1}^2 = \mathbf{V}_k^2 + \mathbf{R} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{p}_k + \mathbf{X} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{q}_k + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot (\Delta \mathbf{c}^2) \quad (16)$$

with

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}_k = \mathbf{p}_{k+1} - \mathbf{p}_k, \quad \Delta \mathbf{q}_k = \mathbf{q}_{k+1} - \mathbf{q}_k \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{c}_k^2 = \mathbf{c}_{k+1}^2 - \mathbf{c}_k^2 \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{p}_k$, $\Delta \mathbf{q}_k$ and $\Delta \mathbf{c}_k^2$ indicate the variations of power injections and line currents at time $k+1$ with respect to the previous time-step k .

Besides the state-space model of the node voltages, the model of the State of Charge (SoC) of the BESS constitutes the second state-space equation for the SMPC. It is written in dependency of the variable $\Delta \mathbf{p}_{k+1}^{\text{BESS}}$, which indicates the variation of active power injections between two time-steps and is later defined as part of the control variables in (25). The model of the SoC is described by:

$$\text{SoC}_{k+1} = \text{SoC}_k - (\mathbf{p}_k^{\text{BESS}} + \Delta \mathbf{p}_{k+1}^{\text{BESS}}) \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{\mathbf{E}_{\text{max}}^{\text{BESS}}} \cdot \eta^{\text{BESS}} \quad (19)$$

where Δt represents the time between the time-steps k and $k+1$, $\mathbf{E}_{\text{max}}^{\text{BESS}}$ denotes the rated energy and η_n^{BESS} the charging and discharging efficiency (considered identical for simplicity).

2) UNCERTAINTY

This work considers the two primary sources of uncertainty in the distribution grid: measurement errors and load and generation forecast errors. Measurement errors stem from unpredictable variations in the behavior of the measurement devices [6]. Load and generation are usually forecasted a day ahead with a resolution of several minutes and constitute the basis for the predictive part of the MPC. Due to unpredictable changes in user behavior and weather conditions, these forecasts underlie an error [51]. The power injections of the controllable BESS are assumed to be known without any error at all times.

Hence, the two sources of uncertainty are modeled as described below.

a) *Measurement error*: Any a-priori known distribution can be used to model the measurement error w_{n,V_k^2} for any node n :

$$w_{n,V_k^2} \sim \text{arbitrary probability distribution} \quad (20)$$

thereby, different distributions can be chosen for each node individually, depending on the characteristics of the measurement devices.

b) *Load and generation forecast error*: Load and generation forecasts for the predicted time-steps $i \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, calculated with respect to the current time-step k , are divided into a deterministic, indicated with a bar (e.g. $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$), and stochastic part, indicated with a hat (e.g. $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$), as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}} = \bar{\mathbf{p}}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}} + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}}, \quad \mathbf{q}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}} = \bar{\mathbf{q}}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}} + \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}} \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}} = \bar{\mathbf{p}}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}} + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}}, \quad \mathbf{q}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}} = \bar{\mathbf{q}}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}} + \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}} \quad (22)$$

As mentioned in the contribution, the proposed SMPC approach is able to explicitly deal with a-priori known probability distributions of any kind, instead of using surrogates like the Chebyshev inequality, which is only accurate for certain probability distributions [52]. Accordingly, active and reactive power load and generation forecast errors are modeled in general as

$$\mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+i}} = \left[\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k+i}^{\text{LD}}, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{k+i}^{\text{DG}} \right]^T \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+i}}$ holds all independent probability distributions of the power injections.

c) *Effect on the voltage*: The node voltages determined by (16) at time $k+1$ depend on both the forecast error of the power injections and the voltage measurement at k . Consequently, taking into account the associated uncertainties, the voltage state \mathbf{V}^2 is considered a stochastic variable, consisting of a deterministic ($\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+1}^2$) and a stochastic ($\hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+1}$) part, according to [19]:

$$\mathbf{V}_{k+1}^2 = \bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+1}^2 + \hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+1}^2(\mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+1}}, \mathbf{w}_{V_k^2}) \quad (24)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+1}^2$ is a function of $\mathbf{w}_{V_k^2}$, the voltage measurement errors, and $\mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+1}}$, the forecast error of the power inputs from generation and load.

This additive uncertainty modeling offers advantages over multiplicative approaches since it isolates probabilistic disturbances from control variables. In additive formulations, the uncertainties are represented as exogenous disturbances added linearly to the system dynamics. This decoupling enables offline computation of stochastic tubes, as the stochastic behavior remains unaffected by so-called online control, which occurs in real-time during the repeated execution of the control. For non-controllable variables (e.g., load), this separation is exact, thus simplifying the incorporation of uncertainty without increasing computational demands during online optimization [19].

However, when control actions directly influence uncertainty (e.g., power curtailments altering the forecast error distributions), additive models introduce conservatism by

neglecting control-dependent uncertainty propagation. For example, curtailing power reduces the operating range, but additive formulations treat forecast errors as a disturbance with a probability distribution defined on the maximum possible interval, overestimating worst-case scenarios [19]. Despite this, it is assumed that the conservatism remains justifiable in control algorithms designed to minimize such curtailments, as reducing curtailments inherently mitigates the discrepancy between modeled and actual uncertainty impacts.

In contrast, multiplicative uncertainty couples disturbances with states and control actions, necessitating online adaptation of stochastic tubes. This increases computational complexity, as the stochastic tube computation must dynamically account for state-dependent noise propagation. Therefore, additive models offer a trade-off between tractability and performance [19].

B. LOSSLESS SMPC

This section first presents the formulation of the Lossless SMPC, which neglects the line loss term in (16). Accordingly, the system behavior becomes linear without any additional measures taken.

1) CONTROL VARIABLES AND POLICY

The variation from the time-step k of active and reactive power injections of DG, load, and the BESS over the time horizon constitute the control variables and are summarized in the control input vector $\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N}$:

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{p} \\ \Delta \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix}_{k+i|k} \quad (25)$$

where the subscript denotes the predicted variables at the future time-step $k+i$ based on the current time-step k .

According to [19], [53], the following equation defines the control law of the MPC:

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k} = K \cdot (\mathbf{V}_{k+i|k}^2 + \mathbf{I}_N \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k^2}) + \boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+i|k} \quad (26)$$

where K denotes the pre-stabilizing feedback gain as the solution of the unconstrained, deterministic linear-quadratic regulator problem, while the online optimization variable $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+i|k} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N}$ can account for operating conditions changing throughout the day by online adaptation to the respective constraints. Specifically, the voltage additive measurement error \mathbf{w}_{V_k} affects the control policy by providing faulty information on \mathbf{V}^2 at each iteration k .

2) STATE-SPACE MODELS

Incorporating the description of the uncertainties in Section III-A2 and the description of the control law in (26), the state-space model of the squared voltage magnitudes results in:

$$\mathbf{V}_{k+i}^2 = \mathbf{V}_{k+i-1}^2 + \mathbf{B} \cdot (\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i}(\mathbf{w}_{V_k}) + \Delta \mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+i}}) \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{X} \end{bmatrix}$.

Conversely, given that, BESS are assumed to be known without any error, the evolution of the SoC does not entail any uncertainty, and thus, (19) can be directly used in the SMPC.

3) OBJECTIVE FUNCTION

The objective function of the Lossless SMPC consists of two parts: a) to use the resources optimally and b) to support the transmission grid. On the other hand, the proposed algorithm does not minimize voltage deviations from the nominal voltage, as the voltage limits can be safely respected due to the stochastic approach. This allows operation closer to the voltage bounds and minimizes other costs.

a) *Use of resources*: The first objective (hereafter defined as *resource objective*) is to minimize power curtailments and the utilization of the large BESS resources. This prevents the waste of any of the generated energy, respectively, to spare the lifetime of the BESS. Accordingly, the deviation of the control input from the nominal value over the specified time horizon, denoted by $T \in \mathbb{N}$, is minimized dependent on the control variable $\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k}$ defined in (25):

$$\min_{\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k}} \sum_{i=1}^T \left\| \mathbf{u}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k} - \mathbf{u}_{\text{nom},k+i} \right\|_{\mathbf{W}} \quad (28)$$

where \mathbf{W} is the weighting matrix and $\mathbf{u}_{\text{nom},k+i}$ is the vector of the nominal values for the control variables, which are given as fixed external inputs.

b) *Transmission grid support*: The second objective (hereafter defined as *support objective*) is to support the transmission grid on the upper voltage level by following a prescribed power injection at the slack node. This objective has gained increasing importance due to the shift of generation resources from the transmission grid to the distribution grid, which demands better bidirectional coordination between the voltage levels [54], [55]. Given that in the Lossless SMPC the line losses are neglected, only the sum of the active power generation and load must equal the given profile p_0 to support the transmission grid as requested. Hence, the objective function is defined as:

$$\min_{\Delta \mathbf{p}_{k+i|k}} \sum_{i=1}^T w \cdot (\mathbf{1}^T (\mathbf{p}_k + \Delta \mathbf{p}_{k+i|k}) - p_{0,k+i} - p_{\text{loss},k+i})^2 \quad (29)$$

where w represents the weighting factor of the objective. In the Lossless SMPC case, the line losses p_{loss} are set to zero, whereas in the Lossy SMPC case, they are assumed to be nonzero. No prescribed profile for reactive power is given, as this work focuses on active power requests for flexibility support [54], [56].

4) HARD CONSTRAINTS

The control variables underlie certain hard constraints that define their operational ranges given by weather conditions, technical limits, or demand. The operational limits refer to the absolute value of the respective power variables, which in turn depend on the optimization variables (defined as variations of

power injections). The constraints are defined independently for each node n , as the individual operating limits vary for each resource.

a) Load and generation: In the context of DGs, active and reactive power are assumed to be controllable. Therefore, the first convex constraint limits the relation between active and reactive power, defined as

$$\tan(\cos(\phi)^{-1}) \cdot \bar{p}_{n,k+i}^{\text{DG}} \geq \bar{q}_{n,k+i}^{\text{DG}} \quad (30)$$

where the required power factor ϕ defines the operation range of the DG and is defined as a fixed external input for each generation resource.

Moreover, the total active and reactive power cannot exceed the nominal apparent power s^{DG} , which is given as a fixed external input, resulting in the second constraint:

$$(\bar{p}_{n,k+i}^{\text{DG}})^2 + (\bar{q}_{n,k+i}^{\text{DG}})^2 \leq (s_{n,k+i}^{\text{DG,nom}})^2 \quad (31)$$

The load has to satisfy a fixed demand:

$$\bar{p}_{n,k+i}^{\text{LD}} = p_{n,k+i}^{\text{LD,nom}}, \quad \bar{q}_{n,k+i}^{\text{LD}} = q_{n,k+i}^{\text{LD,nom}} \quad (32)$$

where $\{p_{n,k+i}^{\text{LD,nom}}, q_{n,k+i}^{\text{LD,nom}}\} \in \mathbf{u}_{k+i}^{\text{nom}}$ are the required active respectively reactive power values, which are not flexible.

b) Energy storage systems: The maximal charging and discharging power and the maximum storage capacity constrain the operation of the large BESS as follows:

$$-p_{\max,n}^{\text{BESS}} \leq \bar{p}_{n,k+i}^{\text{BESS}} \leq p_{\max,n}^{\text{BESS}} \quad (33)$$

$$0 \leq \text{SoC}_{n,k+i} \leq \text{SoC}_{\max,n} \quad (34)$$

5) CHANCE CONSTRAINTS: STOCHASTIC TUBE

Section III-A2 describes the voltage as a probabilistic variable dependent on the other probabilistic variables. Consequently, voltage limitations can only be satisfied with a certain probability:

$$\Pr\{V_{\min}^2 \leq \mathbf{V}_{k+i|k}^2 \leq V_{\max}^2\} \geq 1 - pr_{vio} \quad (35)$$

where $pr_{vio} \in [0, 1)$ denotes the violation probability. (24) splits the voltage state into a deterministic and a stochastic part, which allows for evaluating the system behavior separately. According to [19], the separate parts behave as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i}^2 = \bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i-1}^2 + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i-1}^2 + \boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+i} \quad (36)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i}^2 = \hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i-1}^2 + \mathbf{I}_N \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k} + \mathbf{B} \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i-1}^2 + \mathbf{I}_N \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k})) + \Delta \mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+i}} \quad (37)$$

For simplicity (36) can be rewritten as

$$\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i}^2 = \Phi \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i-1}^2 + \boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+i} \quad (38)$$

with

$$\Phi = \mathbf{I}_N + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{K} \quad (39)$$

Following this simplified equation and predicting multiple time-steps ahead at once, the deterministic voltage state evolution reads as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i}^2 = \Phi^i \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 + H_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\Psi}_k \quad (40)$$

with

$$H_i = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi^{i-1} \cdot \mathbf{B} & \cdots & \mathbf{B} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+1}^T & \boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+2}^T & \cdots & \boldsymbol{\psi}_{k+T}^T \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (42)$$

where $H_i \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 2NT}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Psi} \in \mathbb{R}^{2NT}$. Similarly, (37) can be rewritten as

$$\hat{\mathbf{V}}_{k+i}^2 = \Phi^i \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 + \mathbf{I}_N \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k}) + H_i \cdot \Delta \mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{u}_k} \quad (43)$$

while $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 = 0$ and with

$$\Delta \mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{u}_k} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+1}}^T & \Delta \mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+2}}^T & \cdots & \Delta \mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{u}_{k+T}}^T \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (44)$$

When separating the voltage bounds V_{\min}^2 and V_{\max}^2 of the chance constraint (35) into two equations and applying the previously described voltage state evolution, this reads as

$$e_n \cdot (H_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\Psi}_k + \Phi^i \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 + H_i \cdot \Delta \mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{u}_k} + \Phi^i \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k}) \leq V_{\max}^2 \quad (45)$$

$$e_n \cdot (H_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\Psi}_k + \Phi^i \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 + H_i \cdot \Delta \mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{u}_k} + \Phi^i \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k}) \geq V_{\min}^2 \quad (46)$$

According to Theorem 1 of [52] the deterministic part can be separated from the two stochastic terms, which reads for the upper and lower voltage limit separately as follows:

$$e_n \cdot H_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\Psi}_k + e_n \cdot \Phi^i \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 \leq V_{\max}^2 - \gamma_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, T \quad (47)$$

$$e_n \cdot H_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\Psi}_k + e_n \cdot \Phi^i \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}}_k^2 \leq -V_{\min}^2 + \gamma_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, T \quad (48)$$

The variable γ_i represents the constraint back-off from the deterministic constraint at the predicted time-step i [19]. The combinations of the back-offs for the voltage constraints at all nodes define the stochastic tube, which ensures that the voltage stays within the limits of the prescribed violation probability pr_{vio} .

The value of γ_i is derived by evaluating the violation probability distribution of the two stochastic terms from (45) and (46):

$$\tau_{i,\mathbf{u}} = e_n \cdot H_i \cdot \Delta \mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{u}_k} \quad (49)$$

$$\tau_{i,V} = e_n \cdot \Phi^i \cdot \mathbf{w}_{V_k} \quad (50)$$

Considering generation and load forecast error ($\tau_{i,\mathbf{u}}$), the violation probability depends on the error in each predicted time-step propagated through time according to [19]. In contrast, the voltage measurement error only provides faulty information to the control the time-step k , which corresponds to the moment the voltage measurement is obtained. Accordingly, only this instantaneous error propagates through the control loop described by Φ .

Evaluating equations (49) and (50) is not trivial because adding multivariate probability distributions necessitates multivariate convolutions. However, this can be avoided by discretizing the probability distributions and using numerical convolutions. This explicit use of probability distributions

has another benefit: it allows for the joint assessment of the stochastic behavior resulting from voltage measurement error as well as from the load and generation forecast error. Consequently, it results in a less conservative γ_i , which is obtained by evaluating the joint violation probability distribution in the form of the percentage-point function (ppf) at the prescribed violation probability pr_{vio} as:

$$\gamma_i = ppf(1 - pr_{vio}, \tau_{i,u} + \tau_{i,v}) \quad (51)$$

Since the transient behavior of the distribution grid dissipates within the typical time-step of voltage control, the dynamics alone do not drive the system toward an infeasible state. If the available controllable resources provide sufficient flexibility, the control can stabilize the voltage in the given constraints at all times.

6) FINAL LOSSLESS SMPC FORMULATION

According to the constraints, objective function, and model described above, the Lossless SMPC formulation is hereby summarized. All objectives are quadratic, and all constraints are either convex or linear, thus resulting in a convex optimization problem.

Minimize (28) and (29) for $i = 1, \dots, T$ subject to:

- the control policy (26) with the control input vector (25).
- The recursive voltage state-space model (27) and the SoC of the BESS (19).
- The hard deterministic constraints on the distributed generation (30), (31), consumption (32) and BESS operation (33), (34).
- The probabilistic chance constraints on the nodal voltage state limitations (35), evaluated according to equations (47), (48), (49), (50) and (51).

C. LOSSY GPR SMPC

This section extends the SMPC approach described in Section III-B to include the loss term in the model, as described in the power flow (1). That is, re-introducing the term $\mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{c}^2$ while ensuring that the model used in the SMPC stays linear. In this regard, careful considerations according to the convexity of the optimization problem and acceptable computational load have to be made. Similar to a first-order Taylor approximation, the proposed approach expands around two particular points of interest, i.e., over- and undervoltages. Then, a pre-trained GPR is utilized to address the non-linearity of the loss term in (1). In particular, due to the GPR-feature of ARD, the proposed approach is inherently able to detect and prioritize critical power injections. Contrary to [17], the proposed approach can be used in convex control optimization problems with respect to the power injections.

1) PROPOSED ALGORITHM FOR LOSSY SMPC

Fig. 4 gives an overview of the whole control algorithm and especially the GPR part indicated with the purple shading. The following sections will explain the single parts of the algorithm in more detail.

FIGURE 4. Flow-chart of the Lossy SMPC algorithm.

2) SELECTION OF THE PREDICTION TARGET

The prediction of the loss term is used in three parts of the already presented Lossless SMPC: Firstly, in the state-space model (16) and subsequently in the voltage chance constraints (35). Secondly, in the transmission grid *support objective*, and thirdly, in an additional objective to actively minimize the line losses. This additional objective function can be applied only to the proposed Lossy SMPC, given that it requires the calculation of the loss term. Conversely, this is not applicable to the Lossless SMPC.

In the latter case of the loss minimization, convexity would still be maintained when not directly predicting the squared current c_l^2 but the currents c_l with a subsequent squaring operation. This enables the GPR to capture quadratic trends in the current prediction and increases the prediction accuracy, which is critical when used as a basis for optimization where the gradient of the prediction function is decisive.

This cannot be applied to the *support objective* because the line losses must be subtracted before the minimization's squaring operation. As the voltage chance constraints are enforced as a lower and upper bound, a squaring operation of the optimization variables would lead to non-convexity, resulting

in the choice of c_l^2 as the prediction target for that matter. Furthermore, the GPR should also be included in the linear stochastic tube computation of the Lossless SMPC presented earlier. Consequently, c_l^2 must be predicted directly for the *support objective* and voltage model.

Accordingly, two different GPRs will be trained (see IV in Fig. 4): one with the prediction target $Y_l^2 = c_l^2$ for usage in the voltage chance constraints and *support objective* and one with the prediction target $Y_l = c_l$ for usage in the loss minimization.

3) APPROXIMATION SCHEME FOR LINE LOSSES

To address convexity, a first-order approximation is performed for two different operating points. As the voltage characterizes the state of the system, the data sets are split into overvoltage \bar{V}_{ov} , i.e., when the mean voltage is above 1.0 pu, and the case of undervoltage \bar{V}_{uv} , i.e., mean voltage below 1.0 pu. For each subset, the currents and squared currents are approximated by a linear GPR kernel. More formally, the following decomposition derives

$$\{\bar{V}\} = \{\bar{V}_{1pu}\} \cup \{\bar{V}_{ov}\} \cup \{\bar{V}_{uv}\} \quad (52)$$

where the bar denotes the mean voltage across the whole grid.

4) KERNEL SELECTION

Selecting (7) and thus the kernel (8) is the central aspect in the design of a GPR. According to (52), the linear kernel can be selected for $\{\bar{V}_{over}\}$ and $\{\bar{V}_{over}\}$ individually. The linear covariance function yielding convex optimization reads

$$\kappa(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{I}_{2N} \cdot \sigma_{\bar{V}}^2 \cdot \mathbf{x}'^T \quad (53)$$

where the hyperparameters $\sigma_{\bar{V}}^2 \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2N}$ describes the scaling of each contribution of N active and N reactive power injections. A particularly useful feature of GPR is Automatic Relevance Determination (ARD), which indicates the contribution of each input to a particular prediction [47]. In the given context, this means an automated procedure enabling to detect which node of the underlying system provides a relevant active and reactive power injection for the particular line losses.

5) PRE-DETERMINATION OF LOSSY GPR

To sort the data set and extract the operation areas of the grid into under- and overvoltage cases, the day-ahead load and generation forecasts are employed. They offer a-priori knowledge that can be utilized to simulate the operation for the next day under a plain DMPC containing the objectives and constraints similar to the Lossless SMPC, although excluding the probabilistic formulation (see I in figure 4). The result of the simulation is then used to determine the areas of operation of the grid and to split the training data set. The sorting of the time-steps into under- and overvoltage cases is performed by checking if the predicted mean voltage in the simulation lies below or above 1.0 pu. The power injections resulting from the simulation constitute the basis for the two training set inputs \mathbf{X}_{ov} and \mathbf{X}_{uv} , where the power injections are augmented

with the uncertainty defined in (49) to achieve a robust GPR predictor. Thus, multiple realizations per time-step are added to the respective training sets depending on the number of desired samples (see II in figure 4). The corresponding outputs $Y_{l,uv}$ and $Y_{l,ov}$ are simulated accordingly with the same inputs for all different lines l .

Since each node has both active and reactive power as inputs, the training data has a dimensionality of $2N$ times the number of samples S resulting in $\mathbf{X} = ([\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}]) \in \mathbb{R}^S \times \mathbb{R}^{2N}$. Selecting two different prediction targets ($Y_l = c_l$ and $Y_l^2 = c_l^2$) and given the approximation scheme of two operating areas defined by under- and overvoltage, four training data sets are defined as: $(\mathbf{X}_{uv}, Y_{l,uv})$, $(\mathbf{X}_{ov}, Y_{l,ov})$, $(\mathbf{X}_{uv}, Y_{l,uv}^2)$ and $(\mathbf{X}_{ov}, Y_{l,ov}^2)$, where the subscripts uv and ov define the under- respectively overvoltage case.

The following equations are presented for the case of \mathbf{X}_{ov} , while the equations of \mathbf{X}_{uv} are defined analogously. Equation (53), the training kernel, is defined as

$$K_{ov}(\mathbf{X}_{ov}, \mathbf{X}_{ov}) = \mathbf{X}_{ov} \cdot \mathbf{I}_S \cdot \left(\mathbf{I}_{2N} \cdot \sigma_{V_{ov}}^2 \right) \cdot \mathbf{X}_{ov}^T + \mathbf{I}_{2NS} \cdot \sigma_{noise}^2 \quad (54)$$

The second term in (54) describes a trainable noise hyperparameter $\sigma_{noise}^2 \in \mathbb{R}^+$. The GPR is trained by minimizing (11) with respect to $\sigma_{V_{ov}}^2 = (\dots, \sigma_n^2, \dots)$. Due to ARD, the individual power injections that are not relevant are vanishing, i.e., $\sigma_{V_{ov},n}^2 \rightarrow 0$, for $\sigma_{V_{ov},n}^2 \in \sigma_{V_{ov}}^2$.

To this end, the pre-determinable parts of the Lossy SMPC for each line can be defined as

$$g_l^{ov} = \sigma_{V_{ov}}^2 \cdot \mathbf{X}_{ov}^T \cdot \left(\mathbf{X}_{ov} \cdot \mathbf{I}_S \cdot \left(\mathbf{I}_{2N} \cdot \sigma_{V_{ov}}^2 \right) \cdot \mathbf{X}_{ov}^T + \mathbf{I}_{2NS} \cdot \sigma_{noise}^2 \right)^{-1} \cdot Y_{ov,l}^2 \quad (55)$$

for the squared currents as the prediction target and

$$z_l^{ov} = \sigma_{V_{ov}}^2 \cdot \mathbf{X}_{ov}^T \cdot \left(\mathbf{X}_{ov} \cdot \mathbf{I}_S \cdot \left(\mathbf{I}_{2N} \cdot \sigma_{V_{ov}}^2 \right) \cdot \mathbf{X}_{ov}^T + \mathbf{I}_{2NS} \cdot \sigma_{noise}^2 \right)^{-1} \cdot Y_{ov,l} \quad (56)$$

for the current as the prediction target. For convenience, the kernels addressing all line losses can be written as

$$\mathbf{G}^{ov} = g_1^{ov} \oplus \dots \oplus g_L^{ov}, \quad \mathbf{Z}^{ov} = z_1^{ov} \oplus \dots \oplus z_L^{ov} \quad (57)$$

where (10) is used. Matrices \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{Z} represent the prediction matrices aggregating the results of all individual GPR trainings. Finally, four different GPR predictors with two different prediction targets and training sets dependent on the voltage case are obtained (see V in figure 4).

6) GAUSSIAN PROCESS MODEL FOR SMPC

The inclusion of the GPR predictions into the SMPC algorithm is performed for the following terms: the voltage state-space model, the transmission grid *support objective*, and the line loss minimization objective.

The following equations will no longer explicitly refer to the overvoltage and undervoltage cases but assume that the

applicable case is chosen according to the approximation scheme presented earlier.

a) *Predicted line losses*: The GPR predictor with the target $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{c}^2$ is utilized in the voltage model to ensure the convexity of the optimization problem and the linearity of the stochastic-tube computation. Utilizing (56) and (12) in the proposed application, the predicted line losses read

$$\mathbf{c}^2 = \mathbf{X}^* \cdot \mathbf{G} \quad (58)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^* = [\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}]$ denotes the new data point (integrated in the optimization problem) at which the GPR predictions should be performed. It should be noted that \mathbf{G} is predetermined, i.e., it is a fixed matrix. Therefore, linearity of (58) can be seen by

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{X}_1^* + \mathbf{X}_2^*) \cdot \mathbf{G} &= \left([\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_1] + [\mathbf{p}_2, \mathbf{q}_2] \right) \cdot \mathbf{G} \\ &= \left[\mathbf{G}^T \cdot \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_1^T \\ \mathbf{q}_1^T \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_2^T \\ \mathbf{q}_2^T \end{bmatrix} \right) \right]^T \\ &= \left[\mathbf{G}^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_1^T \\ \mathbf{q}_1^T \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{G}^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_2^T \\ \mathbf{q}_2^T \end{bmatrix} \right]^T \\ &= [\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{q}_1] \cdot \mathbf{G} + [\mathbf{p}_2, \mathbf{q}_2] \cdot \mathbf{G} \\ &= (\mathbf{X}_1^* \cdot \mathbf{G}) + (\mathbf{X}_2^* \cdot \mathbf{G}) \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

$$(\lambda \cdot \mathbf{X}^*) \cdot \mathbf{G} = \lambda \cdot (\mathbf{X}^* \cdot \mathbf{G}) \quad , \forall \lambda \in \mathbb{R} \quad (60)$$

where the linearity of matrix-vector multiplication and $(\mathbf{X}^* \cdot \mathbf{G}) = (\mathbf{X}^* \cdot \mathbf{G})^{TT} = (\mathbf{G}^T \cdot \mathbf{X}^{*T})^T$ is used.

The direct sum decomposition of matrix \mathbf{G} into the parts associated with the active ($n \leq N$) respectively reactive power ($n > N$) inputs and inserting the new matrices into the state-space equation for the voltage results in:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}^2 &= v_0^2 \cdot \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{q} \\ &\quad + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{G}_{n \leq N}^T \cdot \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{G}_{n > N}^T \cdot \mathbf{q}) \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

Summarizing the terms again leads to

$$\mathbf{V}^2 = v_0^2 \cdot \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{R}^G \cdot \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{X}^G \cdot \mathbf{q} \quad (62)$$

with the adjusted lossy real \mathbf{R}^G and imaginary \mathbf{X}^G parts of the admittance matrix:

$$\mathbf{R}^G = \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{G}_{n \leq N}^T \quad (63)$$

$$\mathbf{X}^G = \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{G}_{n > N}^T \quad (64)$$

This result can be directly used to substitute \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{X} in the state-space equation for the voltages (16) and in the constraints back-off equations for the stochastic tube computation described in Section III-B5. Given the linearity of (58) the convexity of the optimization problem holds.

b) *Support objective*: In the case of the *support objective*, the line losses need to be removed from the power provided by the distribution grid to achieve more accurate tracking of the reference trajectory [40]. Accordingly, $p_{\text{loss},k+i}$ in (29) of the

FIGURE 5. Grid topology and placement of distributed resources.

Lossless SMPC is now redefined in the Lossy SMPC as

$$p_{\text{loss},k+i} = \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{G}^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix}_{k+i|k} \quad (65)$$

c) *Loss minimization*: Line loss minimization can be addressed through a different approach: instead of directly taking squared currents and minimizing them quadratically, it is possible to first estimate the currents, square them, and then multiply them by their corresponding line impedances. This transformation allows for capturing quadratic trends in the line loss prediction while still maintaining convexity, as the objective function stays quadratic in the optimization variables while the transformation with the GPR changes the order of magnitude. Accordingly, the currents are included quadratically, but the line loss term, which contains the squared currents, is effectively included linearly. Therefore, it is crucial to note that the weighting factor must be carefully selected to guarantee that the power line losses are effectively weighted against the powers in other parts of the objective, which are included quadratically resulting in another unit respectively order of magnitude [57].

As the total line losses are given by

$$p_{\text{loss}} = \mathbf{c}^T \cdot \text{diag}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{c} \quad (66)$$

and the currents can be predicted with

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{X}^* \cdot \mathbf{Z} \quad (67)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^* = [\mathbf{p}_{k+i|k}, \mathbf{q}_{k+i|k}]$, the objective (hereafter defined as *loss objective*) then results in:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}_{k+i|k}, \mathbf{q}_{k+i|k}} \sum_{i=1}^T \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p} \\ \mathbf{q} \end{bmatrix}_{k+i|k} \cdot \mathbf{Z} \right\|_{\text{diag}(\mathbf{r} \cdot a)} \quad (68)$$

with a denoting the weighting factor of the objective.

It is important to note that equations (65) and (68) use the overall values of $\mathbf{p}_{k+i|k}$ and $\mathbf{q}_{k+i|k}$ to simplify the notation, however these also contain the control variables $\Delta \mathbf{p}_{k+i|k}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{q}_{k+i|k}$ according to (17).

IV. CASE STUDY

Fig. 5 shows the IEEE34 test feeder topology used in this case study, with the locations of the distributed resources indicated.

FIGURE 6. Time profiles of generation, load and power request.

The load and generation profiles, depicted in Fig. 6, are extracted from the simbench case “1-MV-rural-0-sw” [58], a benchmark developed for distribution grid operation. These profiles correspond to the first day of July with 15-minute time-steps ($\Delta t = 0.25h$) and are assigned to the various DGs and loads in the grid. Fig. 6 shows the wind profile “WP7,” which is applied to the wind turbine at node 14, while the PV profiles “PV3” and “PV7” are assigned to the large PVs at nodes 5 and 32, respectively. The bottom plot of the figure presents the daily power profile requested by the transmission grid at the substation level. The power factor for the operation of these DGs is set to $\phi = 0.9$. The commercial load profile “G0-A” is assigned to nodes 5 and 14, “G3-A” to node 18, and one agricultural load profile “L0-A” is assigned to node 32.

The remaining nodes are populated with load and generation profiles of rural low-voltage grids (“rural1”, “rural2”, “rural3”) corresponding to nodes 2 to 31 in the simbench case “1-MV-rural-0-sw” [58]. While the industrial load injects reactive power at a fixed power factor of $\phi = 0.9$, no reactive power is assumed for the rural and agricultural load profiles.

In this test case, load and generation forecast errors are modeled as normally distributed with a 10% standard deviation from the nominal predicted value and a corresponding truncation at 30%. These errors are defined independently for each node and based on the nominal input value $u_{n, \text{nom}, k+i}$:

$$w_{u_{n, k+i}} = \mathcal{N}_{\text{trc}}(0, 10\% \cdot u_{n, \text{nom}, k+i}, 30\% \cdot u_{n, \text{nom}, k+i}) \quad (69)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{\text{nom}, k+i}^{\text{BESS}} = 0$, and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{nom}, k+i}^{\text{DG}} = 0$. Large BESSs with a capacity ($\mathbf{E}_{\text{max}}^{\text{BESS}}$) of 750 kWh each are placed at nodes 4, 9, 17, 20, 25, and 31. These BESSs have a charging and discharging efficiency of 10%, an initial SoC of 50%, and a maximum

FIGURE 7. Weighting of equivalent loss against PV curtailment costs.

power output $\mathbf{p}_{\text{max}}^{\text{BESS}}$ corresponding to a 4-hour utility-scale battery with 187.5 kW.

Power curtailments are penalized with a cost factor of 10 compared to the BESS usage in the objective function. Supporting the transmission grid by following the prescribed power request as closely as possible is rewarded by a cost factor of $w = 30$ because this objective is essential to ensure the overall stability of the electricity grid across different voltage levels. As the power losses are not included quadratically in the objective function in order to obtain better prediction accuracies while maintaining convexity as described in Section III-C6c, its cost factor must be smaller than other power-related parts of the objectives. It is chosen to be $a = 0.05$ to achieve a reasonable weighting against power curtailments, which is visualized in Fig. 7 by comparing the quadratic curtailment cost with the equivalent loss costs after the transformation with the GPR approximation for the range of the maximal expected PV curtailment power. Similar to previous works dealing with MPC for voltage control [22], the proposed SMPC algorithm predicts three time-steps ahead, which equates to a 45-minute horizon and $T = 4$. Extended horizons might not be necessary, as day-ahead optimization is anyhow conducted. However, the proposed method can readily include larger horizons.

Following the outcome of [6], a truncated normal distribution is used to model the measurement error w_{n, V_k^2} for all nodes n as follows:

$$w_{n, V_k^2} = \mathcal{N}_{\text{trc}}(0, \sigma_V^2, 3 \cdot \sigma_V^2) \quad (70)$$

where σ_V denotes the standard deviation parameterized at $\frac{1}{3}\%$, the distribution is truncated at $3 \cdot \sigma_V^2$.

V. RESULTS

An illustration of the validity of the imposed assumption is provided in Sections V-A and V-B. The evaluation of the proposed approach is conducted in its entirety in Section V-C.

A. VALID CHANCE CONSTRAINT

This section presents the verification of the stochastic-tube computation. Fig. 8 compares the summed probability distribution of (49) and (50) with Monte Carlo sampling to verify the computation of the constraint back-offs. The following comparison is presented as an illustrative example for Node 33

FIGURE 8. Verification of constraint back-off computation: Sampling.

FIGURE 9. Verification of constraint back-off computation: PPF function.

at noon, with a predicted duration of 45 minutes. Fig. 9 compares 10,000 samples calculated by Monte Carlo simulation with 10,000 samples from the explicitly calculated distributions using discretization and convolution. Thus, the original probability distributions were discretized at 100 points, and the number of discretization points was kept constant during the multiple convolutions. Due to the relatively low number of discretization points, which keep the computational effort low, the sampling in Fig. 9 appears slightly inaccurate. However, the percentage point function (PPF) in Fig. 8, which is relevant for the calculation of the constraint back-offs γ_i (see (51)), shows almost no error between the Monte Carlo sampling with 10,000 samples (MC10000) and the computation via convolutions (Cnv). The use of Monte Carlo sampling instead of explicit evaluation with convolutions is computationally unattractive. For instance, the calculation with 10,000 samples requires approximately 1,000 times more, and with 100 samples, it requires 10 times more of the convolution computational time. Moreover, 100 samples already lead to a very inaccurate PPF (see figure 8). Consequently, this test shows that the computation of constraint back-offs with numerical convolutions is accurate and more efficient than Monte Carlo sampling.

B. VALID GPR APPROXIMATION

1) APPROXIMATE POINTS OF INTEREST

The validity of the proposed approximation scheme and the GPR results can be seen as follows. Fig. 10 shows the influence of two representative nodes on the line loss approximation for two instances in time and both approximation points, i.e., undervoltage at 2.5 hours and a time of overvoltage at 5 hours. Thereby, the most influential node 14 and one

FIGURE 10. Verification of the proposed GPR approximation scheme.

FIGURE 11. Comparison of influence and scale of the GPR per node.

of the second-most influential nodes, node 9, based on Fig. 11. The dashed blue vertical lines indicate the operating point of the power injection, while the dashed light-blue vertical lines indicate the minimum and maximum power injections of the corresponding day. It can be seen that the fits provided by $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{c}$ capture the actual power losses better than the $\mathbf{Y}^2 = \mathbf{c}^2$ data set. Nevertheless, in all cases, the approximation yields good results in the neighborhood of the operating points. Evident from the contribution to the total power losses, i.e., the scale on the y-axis, node 14 represents a node with high influence on the line losses, while the influence of node 9 is suppressed by a factor of about 5. This establishes deeper characteristics of the proposed GPR approach, which can be described as follows.

2) AUTOMATIC RELEVANCE DETECTION

A useful feature of the proposed GPR is ARD. That means that the proposed approach inherently learns which node contributes relevantly to the total line losses and which contributions can be neglected by adjusting the individual scale parameters $\sigma_{V_n}^2$ for each node. As such, the GPR approximated the relevant nodes with high accuracy, as can be seen, for example, on node 14 of Fig. 10, while the approximation

of less important nodes is automatically neglected. Fig. 11 compares the scale parameters of a GPR with normalized input dimensions and the influence of each node on the line losses, exemplary for the prediction target $Y = c_1$ at 5 hours. It can be seen that high values for the GPR scale parameter (red dotted peaks) are associated with highly influential nodes (blue peaks). Accordingly, the GPR is able to automatically choose more influential nodes as the dominant features of the model by increasing the corresponding individual scale parameters. This can be interpreted as an automatic feature extraction with no dedicated manual selection beforehand.

C. RESULTS FOR LOSSY GPR SMPC

This section presents the results of the developed algorithm. Pandapower was used as a power flow solver to simulate node voltage responses based on optimized control outputs and power profiles [59]. The simulation is executed for each time-step of 15-minute intervals ($\Delta t = 0.25$).

At each time-step, the random samples of load and generation forecast errors, following (49), were added to the power inputs of Fig. 6 to achieve the desired realization of power profiles. Similarly, voltage measurements were obtained from the power flow solution at the previous time-step and augmented with random samples of voltage measurement errors (see (50)) for each time-step independently. To evaluate performance under uncertainty, 100 different realizations of voltage measurements and forecast errors were simulated. At each time-step, the tested control was applied, and its optimized output provided to the power flow solver to simulate the next voltage measurement.

To evaluate the influence of the different SMPC formulations, the incorporation of the lossy model, and the impact of different objective functions, the behavior of the selected distribution grid is tested in response to five different MPCs cases:

- The DMPC where the chance constraints are treated as normal hard constraints without considering uncertainty, will be denoted as -D in the following figures.
- The Lossless SMPC will be denoted as -S.
- The Lossy SMPC will be denoted as -SGP.
- The Lossy SMPC, which additionally to -SGP includes the losses prediction in the *support objective*, will be denoted as -SGP-S.
- The Lossy SMPC which additionally to -SGP-S includes the *loss objective* will be denoted as -SGP-S-L.

1) VOLTAGE MODEL ACCURACY

Fig. 12 presents the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the maximum error in reference to the exact power flow solution for all five MPCs, comparing the use of the linearized and lossy voltage model for the 100 simulated realizations and the whole 24 hours. Even though the lossy voltage model is not used in the lossless MPCs (-D and -S), the lossy voltage resulting from the optimized power injections is calculated as a reference and vice versa. Clearly, the lossy voltage model

FIGURE 12. Root mean square error and maximum error of the voltage solutions comparing linearized and GPRL adjusted model across MPCs.

FIGURE 13. Violations and chance constraint satisfaction.

represents a significant improvement in terms of both the RMSE and the maximum error. The performance of the lossy voltage model slightly differs between the MPCs, given the different objective functions being minimized. Although a maximum error of 0.01 pu does not appear to be significant, this constitutes 20% of the ± 0.05 pu voltage tolerance. The following section evaluates the impact of the model accuracy on the control performance.

2) MPC PERFORMANCE

Fig. 13 summarizes voltage violations and the satisfaction of chance constraints for the different MPC cases. The box-plots show the minimum, maximum, and mean of voltage violations across all time-steps and nodes, while the colored areas show the density of violations. The dashed blue horizontal line represents the chance constraint, which is satisfied when the box plots stay below the line. As expected, -D violates the chance constraint heavily by neglecting the uncertainty completely. The SMPC -S limits the voltage violations significantly and is able to satisfy the chance constraint. Adding the lossy voltage model to the other SMPC cases further limits the voltage violations. The cost analysis determines whether this also leads to an increase in the control costs.

Fig. 14 presents the cost percentage calculated with respect to -D (set to 100 %). -S increases the cost due to the extensive use of the distributed resources, which are needed to limit voltage violations according to the chance constraint. Even though -SGP further limits the voltage violations, it decreases the *resource objective* cost compared to the -S case. As highlighted in the figure, including the line loss prediction in the *support objective* significantly reduces the *support objective* costs in the case of the -SGP-S. In fact, the control benefits

FIGURE 14. Cost comparison of MPC cases with benchmark DMPC.

FIGURE 15. Cost components over time.

from being able to more accurately predict the power at the slack node and thus better follow the prescribed profile. On the contrary, the *loss objective* shows negligible improvements since the resulting costs are low compared to other objectives and that minimizing losses would come at a higher cost of resource utilization.

Fig. 15 shows, in the first three plots from the top, the mean of the costs of the BESS part of the *resource objective*, *loss objective* and *support objective* for the different MPC cases. The fourth plot shows the error between the predicted and the resulting injected power at the transformer, obtained from the simulation. The first noticeable observation is that -SGP-S and -SGP-S-L can better approximate the power at the transformer p_0 , thus resulting in a lower error. As expected, the inclusion of the loss prediction in the *support objective* increases the accuracy of the simulated injected power. Consequently, the *support objective* costs are significantly reduced at almost all times except two time-steps where the *support objective* spikes simultaneously for all SMPC algorithms. This indicates that the distribution grid is not able to provide the requested

TABLE 1. Cost deviation in reference to deterministic MPC.

	D	S	SGP	SGP-S
<i>resource</i> ESS	+0.0%	+54.3%	+36.1%	+36.6%
<i>resource</i> Active	+0.0%	+60.6%	+18.9%	+14.1%
<i>resource</i> Reactive	+0.0%	+11.4%	-76.9%	-63.6%
<i>loss</i>	+0.0%	-18.7%	-15.5%	-13.6%
<i>support</i>	+0.0%	-27.6%	-29.7%	-89.3%
Total	+0.0%	+18.9%	+7.5%	-15.2%

support due to the effectively tighter voltage bounds of the SMPC. Although the two peaks are quite distinct, since the quadratic formulation of costs accentuates the impact of these deviations, they are much less pronounced in terms of injected power. Also noteworthy is that -D has lower storage costs in the last five hours but higher loss costs; the opposite is true for -S. This confirms that the *loss objective* and *resource objective* are traded against each other.

Finally, Table 1 presents the cost variations for the single cost components and in total. Thereby, the significant improvements of the GPR augmentation become obvious, the overall cost reduction of adding the GPR parts to the SMPC (comparing -S and -SGP-S) turns out to be more than 30%, and the individual improvements of the cost components are at least 15% each, scoring the biggest reduction in case of the support objective with more than 60%. Considering absolute numbers, the distribution grid operator must pay for 148 kWh of flexibility due to the error in the loss prediction, comparing -S and SGP-S.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a novel formulation of the power flow equations for distribution grids based on GPR and the integration of the obtained model within the SMPC. This is accomplished by leveraging a-priori knowledge of the controlled system and trajectories so as to generate data and train GPRs offline, while using linear employment during online control. The resulting control framework, namely Lossy SMPC, integrates approximated line losses into the linear power flow equations, thus enabling efficient computation while improving model accuracy.

The results of the validation step verify the employed computation of chance constraints and demonstrate successful approximation of line losses with GPR in both overvoltage and undervoltage scenarios.

The effectiveness of the Lossy SMPC is confirmed through stochastic simulation of a benchmark distribution test system with realistic load and generation profiles. The results demonstrate how the GPR improves voltage model accuracy, positively reduces voltage violations, and minimizes objective costs. Specifically, the low cost of tracking the transmission grid reference offers significant benefit to distribution grid operators by improving the accuracy of power delivery to the transmission level, which in turn reduces the costs.

Future work will focus on developing different sampling strategies around the stochastic tubes and applying the insights of the ARD results for model reduction to enhance scalability. Additionally, integration into hierarchical control structures for distribution grid control with different time scales presents an interesting direction for further research. Furthermore, given its ability to handle various probability distributions, the SMPC will be tested using different distributions for measurement and forecast uncertainties.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Hashemi and J. Østergaard, "Methods and strategies for overvoltage prevention in low voltage distribution systems with PV," *IET Renewable Power Gener.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 205–214, 2017.
- [2] A. Hernandez-Matheus, K. Berg, V. Gadelha, M. Aragüés-Peñalba, E. Bullich-Massagué, and S. Galceran-Arellano, "Congestion-forecast framework based on probabilistic power flow and machine learning for smart distribution grids," *Int. J. Elect. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 156, 2024, Art. no. 109695.
- [3] M. Todescato, J. W. Simpson-Porco, F. Dörfler, R. Carli, and F. Bullo, "Online distributed voltage stress minimization by optimal feedback reactive power control," *IEEE Trans. Control Netw. Syst.*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 1467–1478, Sep. 2018.
- [4] Y. Guo, Q. Wu, H. Gao, X. Chen, J. Østergaard, and H. Xin, "MPC-based coordinated voltage regulation for distribution networks with distributed generation and energy storage system," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1731–1739, Oct. 2019.
- [5] K. P. Kumar and B. Saravanan, "Recent techniques to model uncertainties in power generation from renewable energy sources and loads in microgrids—A review," *Renewable Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 71, pp. 348–358, 2017.
- [6] P. Castello, C. Muscas, and P. A. Pegoraro, "Statistical behavior of PMU measurement errors: An experimental characterization," *IEEE Open J. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 1, 2022, Art. no. 9000509.
- [7] M. Pau, E. D. Din, F. Ponci, P. A. Pegoraro, S. Sulis, and C. Muscas, "Impact of uncertainty sources on the voltage control of active distribution grids," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Smart Energy Syst. Technol.*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [8] D. K. Molzahn and I. A. Hiskens, "A survey of relaxations and approximations of the power flow equations," *Foundations Trends Electric Energy Syst.*, vol. 4, no. 1–2, pp. 1–221, 2019.
- [9] M. Nadeem and A. F. Taha, "Sorta solving the opf by not solving the OPF: DAE control theory and the price of realtime regulation," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 3, pp. 253–265, 2024.
- [10] A. R. Sayed, C. Wang, H. I. Anis, and T. Bi, "Feasibility constrained online calculation for real-time optimal power flow: A convex constrained deep reinforcement learning approach," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 5215–5227, Nov. 2023.
- [11] M. Marković, M. Bossart, and B.-M. Hodge, "Machine learning for modern power distribution systems: Progress and perspectives," *J. Renewable Sustain. Energy*, vol. 15, no. 3, 2023, Art. no. 032301.
- [12] C. Yang et al., "Optimal power flow in distribution network: A review on problem formulation and optimization methods," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 16, 2023, Art. no. 5974.
- [13] D. Tiwari, M. J. Zideh, V. Talreja, V. Verma, S. K. Solanki, and J. Solanki, "Power flow analysis using deep neural networks in three-phase unbalanced smart distribution grids," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 29959–29970, 2024.
- [14] M. Khodayar, G. Liu, J. Wang, and M. E. Khodayar, "Deep learning in power systems research: A review," *CSEE J. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 209–220, Mar. 2021.
- [15] J. B. Hansen, S. N. Anfinssen, and F. M. Bianchi, "Power flow balancing with decentralized graph neural networks," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 2423–2433, May 2023.
- [16] B. Tan et al., "Gaussian processes in power systems: Techniques, applications, and future works," May 2025, *arXiv:2505.15950*.
- [17] M. Marković and B.-M. Hodge, "Parameterized linear power flow for high fidelity voltage solutions in distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 4391–4403, Sep. 2023.
- [18] D. Glover, P. Pareek, D. Deka, and A. Dubey, "Power flow approximations for multiphase distribution networks using Gaussian processes," Apr. 2025, *arXiv:2504.21260*.
- [19] B. Kouvaritakis and M. Cannon, *Model Predictive Control*, (Advanced Textbooks in Control and Signal Processing). Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2016.
- [20] A. Mesbah, "Stochastic model predictive control: An overview and perspectives for future research," *IEEE Control Syst. Mag.*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 30–44, Dec. 2016.
- [21] Z. Wang, J. Wang, B. Chen, M. M. Begovic, and Y. He, "MPC-based voltage/var optimization for distribution circuits with distributed generators and exponential load models," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 2412–2420, Sep. 2014.
- [22] L. Dong, M. Liu, S. Fan, and T. Pu, "A stochastic model predictive control based dynamic optimization of distribution network," in *Proc. IEEE Power Energy Soc. Gen. Meeting*, 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [23] Z. Zhang, F. F. D. Silva, Y. Guo, C. L. Bak, and Z. Chen, "Double-layer stochastic model predictive voltage control in active distribution networks with high penetration of renewables," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 302, 2021, Art. no. 117530.
- [24] G. Song, Q. Wu, J. Tan, W. Jiao, and J. Chen, "Stochastic mpc based double-time-scale voltage regulation for unbalanced distribution networks with distributed generators," *Int. J. Elect. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 155, 2024, Art. no. 109687.
- [25] E. González, J. Sanchis, S. García-Nieto, and J. Salcedo, "A comparative study of stochastic model predictive controllers," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 12, 2020, Art. no. 2078.
- [26] Y. Jiang, C. Wan, J. Wang, Y. Song, and Z. Y. Dong, "Stochastic receding horizon control of active distribution networks with distributed renewables," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 1325–1341, Mar. 2019.
- [27] J. Coulson, J. Lygeros, and F. Dörfler, "Data-enabled predictive control: In the shallows of the deepc," in *Proc. 18th Eur. Control Conf.*, 2019, pp. 307–312.
- [28] J. Berberich, J. Köhler, M. A. Müller, and F. Allgöwer, "Data-driven model predictive control with stability and robustness guarantees," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 66, no. 4, pp. 1702–1717, Apr. 2021.
- [29] S. Kerz, J. Teutsch, T. Brüdigam, M. Leibold, and D. Wollherr, "Data-driven tube-based stochastic predictive control," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 2, pp. 185–199, 2023.
- [30] K. Seel, A. B. Kordabad, S. Gros, and J. T. Gravdahl, "Convex neural network-based cost modifications for learning model predictive control," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 1, pp. 366–379, 2022.
- [31] M. Nonhoff and M. A. Müller, "Online convex optimization for data-driven control of dynamical systems," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 1, pp. 180–193, 2022.
- [32] Z. Marvi and B. Kiumarsi, "Reinforcement learning with safety and stability guarantees during exploration for linear systems," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 1, pp. 322–334, 2022.
- [33] B. Salamat, G. Elsbacher, A. M. Tonello, and L. Belzner, "Model-free distributed reinforcement learning state estimation of a dynamical system using integral value functions," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 2, pp. 70–78, 2023.
- [34] F. Celi, G. Baggio, and F. Pasqualetti, "Distributed data-driven control of network systems," *IEEE Open J. Control Syst.*, vol. 2, pp. 93–107, 2023.
- [35] P. Li, W. Wu, X. Wang, and B. Xu, "A data-driven linear optimal power flow model for distribution networks," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 956–959, Jan. 2023.
- [36] T. Hong, Y. Zhang, J. Liu, D. Zhao, and J. Xiong, "Distributed data-driven optimization for voltage regulation in distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 1263–1273, Jan. 2024.
- [37] Z. Wang et al., "Model-free distributed voltage control for distribution networks based on state space mapping and super-linear feedback," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 6290–6304, Sep. 2024.

- [38] L. Sang, Y. Xu, W. Wu, and H. Long, "Online voltage regulation of active distribution networks: A deep neural encoding-decoding approach," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 4574–4586, Mar. 2024.
- [39] M. Elsheikh, Y. Ortmanns, F. Hecht, V. Roßmann, S. Krämer, and S. Engell, "Trustworthy data-driven model predictive control using a hybrid model with monitoring and adaptation of the domain of validity," *J. Process Control*, vol. 153, 2024, Art. no. 103496.
- [40] E. Schweitzer, S. Saha, A. Scaglione, N. G. Johnson, and D. Arnold, "Lossy distflow formulation for single and multiphase radial feeders," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 1758–1768, May 2020.
- [41] A. Carè, R. Carli, A. D. Libera, D. Romeres, and G. Pillonetto, "Kernel methods and Gaussian processes for system identification and control: A road map on regularized Kernel-based learning for control," *IEEE Control Syst. Mag.*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 69–110, Oct. 2023.
- [42] M. Liu, G. Chowdhary, B. C. D. Silva, S.-Y. Liu, and J. P. How, "Gaussian processes for learning and control: A tutorial with examples," *IEEE Control Syst. Mag.*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 53–86, Oct. 2018.
- [43] T. X. Nghiem, "Linearized Gaussian processes for fast data-driven model predictive control," in *Proc. Amer. Control Conf.*, 2019, pp. 1629–1634.
- [44] L. Hewing, J. Kabzan, and M. N. Zeilinger, "Cautious model predictive control using Gaussian process regression," *IEEE Trans. Control Syst. Technol.*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 2736–2743, Nov. 2020.
- [45] M. Baran and F. Wu, "Network reconfiguration in distribution systems for loss reduction and load balancing," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1401–1407, Apr. 1989.
- [46] E. D. Din, M. Pau, F. Ponci, and A. Monti, "A coordinated voltage control for overvoltage mitigation in LV distribution grids," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 8, 2020, Art. no. 2007.
- [47] C. Rasmussen and C. Williams, *Gaussian Processes for Machine Learning* (Adaptive Computation and Machine Learning). Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, Jan. 2006.
- [48] M. Zimmer, D. Carta, T. Pesch, and A. Benigni, "Signal recovery in power systems by correlated Gaussian processes," *IEEE Open J. Ind. Electron. Soc.*, vol. 5, pp. 692–703, 2024.
- [49] B. Banfield, D. A. Robinson, and A. P. Agalgaonkar, "Distributed MPC of residential energy storage for voltage regulation and peak shaving along radial distribution feeders," *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 1413–1424, Jun. 2021.
- [50] X. Zhou, M. Farivar, Z. Liu, L. Chen, and S. H. Low, "Reverse and forward engineering of local voltage control in distribution networks," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 1116–1128, Mar. 2021.
- [51] G. Mancò, U. Tesio, E. Guelpa, and V. Verda, "A review on multi energy systems modelling and optimization," *Appl. Thermal Eng.*, vol. 236, 2024, Art. no. 121871.
- [52] B. Kouvaritakis, M. Cannon, S. V. Raković, and Q. Cheng, "Explicit use of probabilistic distributions in linear predictive control," *Automatica*, vol. 46, no. 10, pp. 1719–1724, 2010.
- [53] J. Fleming and M. Cannon, "Stochastic MPC for additive and multiplicative uncertainty using sample approximations," *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, vol. 64, no. 9, pp. 3883–3888, Sep. 2019.
- [54] A. Agarwala et al., "Towards next generation power grid transformer for renewables: Technology review," *Eng. Rep.*, vol. 6, no. 4, 2024, Art. no. e12848.
- [55] T. Basso and R. DeBlasio, "IEEE 1547 series of standards: Interconnection issues," IEEE, Tech. Rep. 5, 2004.
- [56] H. Früh, S. Müller, D. Contreras, K. Rudion, A. V. Haken, and B. Surmann, "Coordinated vertical provision of flexibility from distribution systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 1834–1844, Mar. 2023.
- [57] R. Halvgaard, L. Vandenberghe, N. K. Poulsen, H. Madsen, and J. B. Jørgensen, "Distributed model predictive control for smart energy systems," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1675–1682, May 2016.
- [58] S. Meinecke et al., "SimBench—A benchmark dataset of electric power systems to compare innovative solutions based on power flow analysis," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 12, 2020, Art. no. 3290.
- [59] L. Thurner et al., "Pandapower—An open-source Python tool for convenient modeling, analysis, and optimization of electric power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 6510–6521, Nov. 2018.

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